

Denmark | One Health Surveillance | Shiga Toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC)

Background

WGS-based STEC surveillance has been hampered by the increased use of culture-independent diagnostic tests (CIDT) in diagnostic laboratories

Objectives

- To test a procedure for referral of STEC-positive faecal samples from one clinical laboratory to the National Reference Laboratory (NRL)
- To set up a laboratory procedure for the isolation and further characterization of

Outcomes & Impact

- Established collaboration with one clinical laboratory that sent 140 STEC-positive samples to the NRL
- A number of methods for culturing and confirmation of STEC were tested. This knowledge forms an important basis for further work on implementing an efficient procedure for securing STEC isolates for One Health Surveillance

Lessons learned

- An important disadvantage of performing initial diagnostics in the regional laboratory and culturing of CIDT-positive samples at the NRL is the delay in culturing and thereby the loss of viability
- It is now important to setup a real-time PCR to obtain results faster and thereby a smoother procedure for isolation of STEC

Core messages

- The rapid conversion to CIDT will give a huge setback in the surveillance and outbreak detection unless procedures and methodologies are adapted to the new situation, for which transfer of isolation to the NRL is a solution
- More innovative solutions should also be explored, e.g. culture-independent typing of the pathogens directly in the complex samples